

Phytochemical screening and molluscicidal effect of *Tridax procumbens* L. (Wild daisy) crude leaf extract against *Pomacea canaliculata* (Golden apple snail)

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Abstract

Pomacea canaliculata, commonly known as golden apple snail, is considered as one of the serious pests of rice in the Philippines. However, synthetic molluscicides used to manage golden apple snails are also a significant problem due to harmful effects to the environment and human health. This study was conducted to investigate the presence of phytochemicals and molluscicidal effect of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) crude leaf extract against *Pomacea canaliculata*. Qualitative phytochemical analysis was done to determine the bioactive compounds as molluscicide present in *Tridax procumbens* L. such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and sterols. *Pomacea canaliculata* with shell diameter of 11-16 mm and 23-28 mm were exposed to different concentrations (25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%) of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract. Mortality of *Pomacea canaliculata* was determined by probing with a needle to which snail gives no response. Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and sterols were observed in the crude leaf extract of *Tridax procumbens* L. No significant differences between the mortality of small and large *Pomacea canaliculata* were observed among the concentrations of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract. Evaluating the percentage mortality of small and large *Pomacea canaliculata*, 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract exhibited the highest percentage mortality, followed by 75%, 50%, and 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts. These results demonstrate the possibility of using *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract as a molluscicide against *Pomacea canaliculata*. Additional research should be conducted to determine the molluscicidal effect of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract against other life stages of *Pomacea canaliculata*.

Keywords: *Pomacea canaliculata*; Molluscicidal effect; Phytochemical screening; *Tridax procumbens*; Crude leaf extract.

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Introduction

Pomacea canaliculata, commonly known as golden apple snail, is a freshwater mollusc that belongs to the family Ampullariidae. It is suited for living in swamps, marshes, ditches, irrigation canals, ponds, lakes lined with vegetation, and agricultural areas such as rice paddies and taro patches (Cowie et al., 2013).

Golden apple snail was introduced intentionally in Asia as a food item and an export commodity for gourmet restaurants (Naylor, 1996). In Malaysia, *Pomacea canaliculata* is used as an alternative feed to ducks and processed as an organic fertilizer (Salleh et al., 2012). Raw golden apple snails are considered as a delicacy in China. In the Philippines, *Pomacea canaliculata* is a meal for fish, shrimp, and prawn farming (Cowie et al., 2013). It is also popular in the aquarium industry due to its appearance and golden shell color (Chaichana & Sumpan, 2015).

Its voracious appetite and ability to breed rapidly are some of the most alluring features of the *Pomacea canaliculata* for entrepreneurs. Vast quantities of snails can be produced for market within a short period of time with low investment costs in terms of initial outputs.

Nevertheless, the extensive reproduction and wide distribution of golden apple snails had resulted in a drastic devastation in the agricultural systems. Golden apple snail has become a serious pest of crops such as rice, lotus, taro, swamp cabbage, mat rush, watercress, parsley, water chestnuts, wild rice, azolla, and water lilies (Hollingsworth & Cowie, 2006). In the Philippines, farmers have considered *Pomacea canaliculata* as the most serious pest of rice. Accordingly, it can destroy one square meter of rice field overnight. This damage can lead to more than 50% yield losses (Rice Knowledge Bank, n.d.). Statistics revealed that a total of \$1.47 billion was estimated in terms of crop damage caused by golden apple snail in Southeast Asian countries every year (de Brito & Joshi, 2016). Reports also showed that about 1.4 million ha of rice fields in the Philippines were infested by *Pomacea canaliculata* in 2003 (Cowie et al., 2013). The annual destruction cost of *Pomacea canaliculata* to the Philippine rice agriculture had increased with an estimated cost of 731-2,064 million USD per annum (Nongnutch & Nanuam, 2016).

The demand to take management actions to control *Pomacea canaliculata* increases due to its negative implications to the agricultural sector. Numerous suggestions for sustainable management methods of the pest snail have been made considering the implication to the other organisms and ecosystem. In most countries, the government advises farmers to use molluscicides to suppress golden apple snail. In Southeast Asia, the two major active agents of commercial molluscicides to suppress *Pomacea canaliculata* are metaldehyde and niclosamide (Schneiker et al., 2016).

Consequently, recent news depicted that standard molluscicidal agents such as metaldehyde and niclosamide are detrimental to the environment and non-target organisms (de Brito & Joshi, 2016). Accordingly, metaldehyde and niclosamide are effective against *Pomacea canaliculata* but harmful to the growth of rice seedling and toxic for freshwater organisms. They serve as pollutants of groundwater lakes and rivers (Schneiker et al., 2016). Furthermore, synthetic molluscicides also have side effects to humans, especially to rice farming communities (de Brito & Joshi, 2016).

The agricultural sector is conscious of the problems caused by the chemical molluscicides. Several researches have recently been carried out to address this problem. Studies have shown the importance of plant extracts as alternative molluscicides to control *Pomacea canaliculata*. Many plant species such as *Mimosa pudica* L. (sensitive plant), *Adriana quadripartite* (bitter bush) and *Sphagneticola trilobata* (Singapore daisy) (Nongnutch & Nanuam, 2016), *Azadirachtin indica* (neem) (Massaguni & Latip, 2012), and *Camellia oleifera* (oil-seed camellia) (Kijprayoon et al., 2014), were also used and have been demonstrated to have molluscicidal properties against *Pomacea canaliculata*. In the Philippines, Demetillo et al. (2015) have investigated the effect of *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemon grass) crude leaf extracts against *Pomacea canaliculata*. Results showed that lemon grass crude leaf extract can increase the mortality rates on both adults and juvenile stages of *Pomacea canaliculata*. However, *Cymbopogon citratus* is used in the Philippines as a condiment and in food industry such as alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages, frozen dairy desserts, confectionary, baked foods, gelatin, pudding, and meat products (Cowie et al., 2013).

With a limited amount of research dealing with the management of *Pomacea canaliculata* using organic molluscicides in the Philippines, the authors of this paper wanted to address the challenge of exploiting local plants as alternative molluscicides to combat golden apple snails.

Given this challenge, the researchers conducted a study that investigated the phytochemicals and molluscicidal effects of *Tridax procumbens* L. against *Pomacea canaliculata*. The research authors wanted to share a more economical and practical way to control golden apple snails. It aimed to help the agricultural sector, especially the local farmers in controlling *Pomacea canaliculata* using *Tridax procumbens* L., which is a weed, not widely used and randomly distributed in the Philippines. *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract is also a great help considering that it is safe, and the effect might not have significant difference compared to commercially used molluscicides that have drawbacks to the environment and hazardous to non-target organisms and human health.

The main objective of the study was to investigate the phytochemicals and molluscicidal effect of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract against *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail). Specifically, the study determined the bioactive components present in the crude leaf extract of *Tridax procumbens* L., and percentage mortality of *Pomacea canaliculata* after the application of different treatments (25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%) of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract. The authors also sought to determine the level of significance of the difference between the mortality of small and large *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) at various concentrations.

Methods

A. Collection of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) leaves

Twenty kilograms of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) leaves were collected from a rice field at Brgy. Mambog III, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines. The collected leaves were placed in a plastic bag and were prepared for laboratory use.

B. Extraction and preparation of *Tridax procumbens* (wild daisy) crude leaf extract

Collected leaves of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) were washed with 20 L distilled water to remove dust and unwanted materials. Two hundred fifty grams of washed *Tridax procumbens* L. leaves were measured using a weighing scale, placed in a nylon net bag, and air-dried by hanging at the science laboratory of SHS in San Nicholas III, Bacoor City for five days. Dried leaves were placed in a plastic bag and were ground into fine powder using an electric blender and were weighed using a top-loading balance. One hundred grams of powdered *Tridax procumbens* L. leaves were soaked with 800 mL of 95% ethanol in a 3.5 L cater plan. These were capped by parafilm followed by an aluminum foil and were stored for six days. The soaked solution was filtered using muslin cloth. The filtered ethanol extract was subjected to rotary evaporation to obtain the *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract. A semi-solid crude leaf extract was collected and placed in a glass jar.

C. Phytochemical Analysis

Thirty grams of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) crude leaf extract was subjected to qualitative phytochemical analysis at SHS in San Nicholas III, Bacoor City. Qualitative phytochemical analysis was conducted to determine the bioactive components present in the crude extract of *Tridax procumbens* L. leaves such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and sterols. The following tests were carried out using *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract using standard procedures adapted from Hussain et al.'s (2011) study.

a. Alkaloids Test

One gram of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract was measured using analytical balance and placed in a test tube. Five drops of Wagner's reagent, which was prepared through dissolving two grams of iodine and six grams of potassium iodide in 100 mL distilled water, was added. The presence of reddish-brown color indicates the presence of alkaloids.

b. Flavonoids Test

One milliliter of 10% ethanol and 0.5 mL of 10% HCl were measured and mixed with two grams of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract. The solution was added with magnesium metals. Formation of reddish color indicates the presence of flavonoids.

c. Saponins Test

Two grams of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract was measured using analytical balance and placed in a test tube. Five milliliters of distilled water were added. The solution was shaken vigorously for 15 minutes. The persistence of a stable froth indicates the presence of saponins.

d. Sterols Test

Five grams of *Tridax procumbens* L. was added with 10 mL chloroform and filtered using Whatman filter paper no. 1. The filtrate was added with two drops of sulfuric acid. The solution was shaken and let stand for 10 minutes. Formation of a golden yellow color indicates the presence of sterols in the sample.

D. Collection of *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) and setting up of the containers

Three hundred sixty *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) was collected from a rice field at Brgy. Mambog III, Bacoor City, Cavite. Golden apple snails with shell diameter of 11-16 mm and 23-28 mm were measured using a Vernier caliper. Each size of *Pomacea canaliculata* was placed in a pail, covered with nylon net and secured with rubber band to prevent from escaping, and transported to the SHS in San Nicholas III, Bacoor City, Cavite.

Ten *Pomacea canaliculata* of each size were placed in one liter plastic container, which was purchased at Brgy. Molino II, Bacoor City, Cavite. Each container containing ten *Pomacea canaliculata* was fed per day with seven grams of banana leaves, which were collected from a rice field at Brgy, Mambog III, Bacoor City, Cavite. *Pomacea canaliculata* was acclimated to laboratory conditions for seven days.

E. Preparation of different concentrations of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) crude leaf extract

Tridax procumbens L. (wild daisy) crude leaf extract was dissolved in distilled water to obtain test concentrations, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%. To obtain 25% concentration, 50 g of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract was diluted in 200 mL distilled water. To obtain 50% concentration, 100 g of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract was diluted with 200 mL distilled water. One hundred fifty grams of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract was diluted in 200 mL distilled water to obtain 75% concentration. One hundred percent concentration of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract was also used in the study. One pack of niclosamide and metaldehyde wettable powders, the positive controls, were purchased from an agricultural merchandise store at Las Piñas City. One gram of metaldehyde wettable powder was measured using analytical balance and dissolved in 200 mL distilled water. One gram of niclosamide wettable powder was also measured and dissolved in 258 mL distilled water.

F. Testing of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) crude leaf extract against *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail)

Ten *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) was maintained in each one-liter plastic container with 30 snails total per each concentration for each treatment of different sizes. Thirty milliliters of test solutions were measured using 100 mL beaker and poured in 100 mL atomizer spray bottles. Test solutions were sprayed in each container. These containers were covered with a nylon net and were secured with a rubber band to prevent the golden apple snails from escaping. *Pomacea canaliculata* was exposed with test solutions for 24 hours. Golden apple snails were deprived of food during the exposure of controls.

G. Monitoring of setup and recording of data

After the 24 hour exposure, *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) was transferred from test solutions to 50 mL distilled water and kept for 24 hours. Mortality of golden apple snails was observed after 24 hours and determined by probing with a needle in the operculum to elicit withdrawal movement. Dead *Pomacea canaliculata* was identified if it will remain immobile and will not retract or hang out of the shell. Mortality of *Pomacea canaliculata* was recorded.

H. Statistical Analysis

Percentage mortality of different sizes of *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) in each treatment was computed. The number of dead snails in each treatment was divided by the total number of snails per treatment multiplied by 100. Data were statistically analyzed using Two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Two-way ANOVA was used to determine the statistical significance to determine the statistical significance between the sizes of *Pomacea canaliculata*.

Results and Discussion

Qualitative phytochemical analysis is shown in Figure 1. Results showed that alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and sterols were identified in the crude leaf extract of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy).

Figure 1. Qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) crude leaf extract

Legend: A - Alkaloids Test (Positive, reddish brown coloration); B - Flavonoids Test (Positive, reddish coloration); C - Saponins Test (Positive, froth formation); D - Sterols Test (Positive, yellow coloration)

For alkaloids test, the appearance of red coloration which indicates the presence of alkaloids was observed. The appearance of reddish coloration in the *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract noted a positive reaction in the flavonoids test. For the saponins test, formation of froth which indicates the presence of saponins was observed. Also, the appearance of yellowish coloration which indicates the presence of sterols was observed.

These bioactive components such as saponins have a high toxic effect against *Pomacea canaliculata*. The application of organic molluscicides with saponin as bioactive component destroys the red blood cells by means of hemolysis and therefore reduce oxygen uptake and alter hemoglobin concentrations (Clearwater et al., 2008).

As indicated in Figure 2, in the molluscicidal assay of small *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) with a shell diameter of 11 mm - 16 mm, metaldehyde and niclosamide wettable powders, the positive controls, exhibited the highest number of killed *Pomacea canaliculata* with a percentage mortality of 100.0, then followed by 100% and 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts with percentage mortality of 90.00 and 80.00, respectively. Fifty percent *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract exhibited a percentage mortality of 76.67. Meanwhile, 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract showed the least number of killed *Pomacea canaliculata* with a percentage mortality of 70.00.

Figure 2. Percentage mortality of small *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail)

Legend: A - 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; B - 50% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; C - 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; D - 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; E - metaldehyde wettable powder; F - niclosamide wettable powder

Niclosamide also exhibited the highest number of killed large *Pomacea canaliculata* (23 mm-28 mm) with a percentage mortality of 100.0 followed by niclosamide, 97.00. Then, it was followed by 100% and 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts with percentage mortality of 93.33 and 83.33, respectively. Fifty percent *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract exhibited a percentage mortality of 76.67 while 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract showed the least number of killed *Pomacea canaliculata*, 66.67%. The results of percentage mortality of large *Pomacea canaliculata* is shown in Figure 3.

Bioactive compounds such as saponins have a high toxic effect against *Pomacea canaliculata*. *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract contains saponins which is one of the good properties of an organic molluscicide. The application of organic molluscicides with saponin destroys the red blood cells by means of hemolysis and therefore reduce oxygen uptake and alter hemoglobin concentrations (Clearwater et al., 2008). Furthermore, the effect of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract against *Pomacea canaliculata* was observed within two days after the application which corresponds to the two to three days duration of a good molluscicide to kill *Pomacea canaliculata* (Sebastian, 2001).

Figure 3. Percentage mortality of large *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail)

Legend: A - 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; B - 50% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; C - 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; D - 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; E - metaldehyde wettable powder; F - niclosamide wettable powder

The significant variations between the mortality of small and large *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) at various concentrations were investigated using two-way Analysis of Variance. The results of ANOVA indicate that significant differences among the treatments were observed. The results of two-way ANOVA are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Difference between the mortality of small and large *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) at various concentrations using two-way ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	Df	Ms	F	P	F crit	Remarks
Total	43.06	359	-	-	-	-	-
Between Sizes	0.00	1	0.00	0.00	0.10	3.87	Not Significant
Within Treatments	4.79	5	0.96	8.73	0.00	2.24	Significant
Sizes x Treatments	0.07	5	0.01	0.12	0.99	2.24	Significant

Since there are significant differences among the treatments used, Tukey's HSD was employed to determine which among the concentrations had significant variations. It was identified that there is no significant difference between the mortality of small and large *Pomacea canaliculata* in 25% and 50% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts; 25% and 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts; 50% and 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts; 50% and 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts; 75% and 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts; 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract and metaldehyde; 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract and niclosamide; and metaldehyde and niclosamide.

Nevertheless, there is a significant difference between the mortality of small and large *Pomacea canaliculata* in 25% and 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts; 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract and metaldehyde; 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract and niclosamide; 50% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract and metaldehyde; 50% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract and niclosamide; 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract and metaldehyde; and 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract and niclosamide.

Table 2. Tukey's HSD test for the mortality of small and large *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail) in Treatments A, B, C, D, E, and F

Treatments	q _s	q'	Remarks
A vs B	1.95	3.86	Not significant
A vs C	3.12		Not significant
A vs D	5.45		Significant
A vs E	7.01		Significant
A vs F	7.4		Significant
B vs C	1.17		Not significant
B vs D	3.51		Not significant
B vs E	5.06		Significant
B vs F	5.45		Significant
C vs D	2.34		Not significant
C vs E	3.9		Significant
C vs F	4.29		Significant
D vs E	1.56		Not significant
D vs F	1.95		Not significant
E vs F	0.39		Not significant

Legend: A - 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; B - 50% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; C - 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; D - 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract; E - metaldehyde wettable powder; F - niclosamide wettable powder

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, *Tridax procumbens* L. (wild daisy) crude leaf extract has a molluscicidal activity against *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail). It was found out that all the prepared test concentrations, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts, were able to kill at least 50% of the total number of exposed *Pomacea canaliculata*. It was noted that higher concentration of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract was more effective in terminating *Pomacea canaliculata*. It was also found out that 25% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract is as good as 50% and 75% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts, and 50% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract is as good as 75% and 100% *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extracts.

The effect of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract against *Pomacea canaliculata* was observed within two days after the application which corresponds to the two to three days duration of a good molluscicide. The mortality of *Pomacea canaliculata* is attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds as molluscicide such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins and sterols in the crude leaf extract of *Tridax procumbens* L. The findings of the study have demonstrated the possibility of using substances derived from plants, specifically of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract as an organic molluscicide to terminate *Pomacea canaliculata*.

Recommendations

The study might open more possibilities to find alternative options for plant pest management, specifically in addressing the agricultural problems caused by *Pomacea canaliculata* (golden apple snail). Considering the findings of the study, the researchers would like to recommend the following for further development and improvement of results found in this study:

1. Testing of the molluscicidal activity of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract against other life stages of *Pomacea canaliculata*.
2. Field testing of the molluscicidal activity of *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract against *Pomacea canaliculata*.
3. Conducting quantitative phytochemical analysis of *Tridax procumbens* L. in order to determine the number of bioactive compounds as a molluscicide such as alkaloids, flavonoids, sterols and saponins present in the plant.
4. Extraction of the bioactive compounds as a molluscicide present in the *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract to be used against *Pomacea canaliculata*. Concentration of these bioactive components can contribute to the molluscicidal effect of the plant.
5. Utilization of other local weeds that have a potential to kill *Pomacea canaliculata*.
6. Use of other *Tridax* species aside from *Tridax procumbens* L. to kill *Pomacea canaliculata*.
7. Use of other *Pomacea* species aside from *Pomacea canaliculata* as the subject to be killed by *Tridax procumbens* L. crude leaf extract.

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